
D-JIP2-4.4.1 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES IN EJP COHESIVE WP4

**Workpackage 4: Data platform to
facilitate risk-analysis and
outbreak control**

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: IZSAM, BfR

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D-JIP2-4.4.1 Each subtask conducts workshops, provides documentation and tutorials
WP and Task	WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control WP4-T4: Dissemination
Leader	BfR
Other contributors	IZSAM, BfR
Due month of the deliverable	42
Actual submission month	48 (The EJP COHESIVE project was extended. Dissemination activities were therefore continued until the end of the project)
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES IN EJP COHESIVE WP4

Marion Gottschald¹, Birgit Lewicki¹, Jakub Fusiak¹, Valentina Caldarelli², Iolanda Mangone², Adriano Di Pasquale², Christin Wallstab¹, Robert Opitz¹, Thomas Selhorst¹, Armin Weiser¹

¹ German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)

² Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise Giuseppe Caporale (IZSAM)

In One Health EJP COHESIVE WP4, free and open source web tools were developed to improve the efficiency of risk analysis, including risk assessment and outbreak management. In **WP4.1**, the prototype **COHESIVE information system (CIS)** (<https://cohesive.izs.it/>) was developed to help integrate pathogen information (whole genome sequencing data and related metadata) from the human and veterinarian side at the Member State level. The **FoodChain-Lab web application (FCL Web; WP4.2)** (<https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>) as a joint output of EJP COHESIVE and EFSA projects helps tracing suspicious food items along global supply chains during foodborne incidents and unifies tracing data visualisation, analysis and reporting in one modular framework. The **shiny Risk** application developed in **WP4.3** is a web application supporting risk assessors in conducting probabilistic quantitative risk assessments. To create awareness about the tools for potential users, several dissemination activities took place.

From 2018 and over the whole project duration FCL Web was presented during several **dissemination activities of other projects** as integrative tracing tool and reference to COHESIVE was given. Shiny Risk is part of the **European Food Risk Assessment Training Programme (EU-FORA)**, which is an important initiative to prepare for future risk assessment needs. Lectures on shiny Risk are also regularly held at **German universities**. The WP4 tools were also presented at all **annual COHESIVE meetings** (2018-2020) and at the **COHESIVE end symposium** (2021) in presentations as well as interactive exercises and workshops for the COHESIVE community and other interested user.

In **2019**, the dissemination task in COHESIVE WP4 started officially and shiny Risk was presented at the DACH Epidemiologietagung.

WP4 activities were presented at the **2020 One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting** in an online format (presentation and poster on CIS, poster on FCL Web). In 2020 FCL Web became part of the **SISOT tool box**. The CIS was introduced at the Italian National Reference Centre GENPAT Annual national workshop in a virtual event.

Many dissemination activities for COHESIVE took place in **2021**. WP4 tools were presented at the **One Health EJP CPD module "Digital Innovation for One Health Practitioners"** (<https://onehealthjep.eu/cpd-2021/>). In the framework of the OHEJP CPD module, FCL Web was presented in an interactive virtual event (presentations, interactive live demo, interactive traceability exercise) and in an e-learning course developed in a project with EFSA. Shiny Risk was presented during the digital innovation sharing forum of the CPD module. In the framework of the **Online Advanced Course on "Innovative tools and methods for ensuring seafood authenticity"** (<https://edu.iamz.ciheam.org/SeafoodAuthenticity/en/>), FCL Web was introduced to the participants and an interactive live demo as well as an interactive traceability exercise using FCL Web was conducted. During the **One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Workshop "Online Software Fair"** (<https://onehealthjep.eu/asm-satellite-workshop-2021/>) a pitch presentation and a dedicated session (presentation and interactive live demo) on FCL Web was conducted. Furthermore, FCL Web was shown as a poster during the 2021 **One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting** in an online format. The work done within COHESIVE is also highlighted in the **final report of a project with EFSA** which will be published soon. Results and impact of COHESIVE in general and particularly of FCL Web and shiny Risk were presented at the **German OH EJP Mirror Group meeting** for stakeholders like e.g.

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the German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture. Shiny Risk was introduced at the **DACH Epidemiologietagung** in a poster session. The CIS was presented at the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop in Italy and a **publication** on the "Refinement of the COHESIVE Information System towards a unified ontology of food terms for the public health organizations" was published as well (<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2969/paper11-IFOW.pdf>).